

THE INDIRECT SPEECH AND THE MICROTEXT

(in German, Uzbek and Russian languages)

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Abstract: The article discusses the occurrence of acquired speech in German, Uzbek and Russian languages in microtext. First of all, the factors that create the integrity of the text are listed. Then, the morphological type of acquired speech characteristic of the Uzbek and German languages is analyzed in terms of component, contextual and text.

Key words: microtext, direct and indirect speech, syntactic acquisition speech, morphological acquisition speech.

The communicative integrity of the microtext is formed in two ways. First of all, the microtext consists of a chain connection of its components. Each subsequent sentence in the microtext communicatively continues the information based on the preceding sentence. As a result, a theme-rhematic chain is formed, the end of which marks the limit of the microtext. Thus, the theme-rhematic chain performs the task of creating a text [Wittmers, 1970, 115, 109; Moskalskaya, 1981, 21]. Secondly, in the communicative analysis of the text, researchers such as W. Schmidt, W. Harweg, M. Pfütze, H. Isenberg use the term communicative goal or communicative task. In traditional syntax, there are three main types of communicative purpose defined for a sentence: 1) indication, 2) question and 3) command. These are also attributed to the text [Moskalskaya, 1981, 58–59]. Both points of view are recognized in Uzbek linguistics [To‘xsanov, 1987; Jumaev, 2021]. The structural integrity of the text has been widely studied in German studies and Russian linguistics [Pfütze, 1970; Dressler, 1972; Loseva, 1973; Heidolph, 1966; van Dijk, 1972; Isenberg, 1972].

According to scientists, structural integrity is a means of expression of textual and communicative integrity. Such tools include personal, demonstrative and possessive pronouns, pronouns, articles, tenses, number, homonyms, similar keywords, lexical repetition, tense and place, conjunctions, linking words as well as loading and modal-input words. These devices are involved in the production of text by serving to indicate the relationship of the sentence in which it is used to the preceding or following sentence(s). For example, if the sentence *Der Schwan und ihr Boot glitten lautlos aneinander vorüber* is taken separately, the reason why the definite article (*der*) and the possessive pronoun (*ihr*) are used becomes unclear. And the speech will not be structurally complete and complete. These tools contain forward-looking statements. Therefore, it is necessary to refer to the previous statements. Only then will completeness be achieved not only in terms of structure, but also in terms of content and communication: *Im Kanal lag ein Boot; sie mieteten es und schwammen dahin. Ein Schwan kam ihnen entgegen. Der Schwan und ihr Boot glitten lautlos aneinander vorüber* (H. Mann).

In the following microtext, the means of expressing wholeness differ from the above: *Marcel erwachte mit entsetzlichen Schmerzen in der Schulter. Bürger Buzot hatte ihn auf falsche Seite gelegt* (W. Bredel). The personal pronoun (*ihn*) is used instead of the proper noun (Marcel) in the first sentence, and the event that happened after the plusquamperfect is clear (expressed in the imperfect). So, two sentences connected in terms of structure and content together form a microtext [Moskalskaya, 1981, 26].

Due to the fact that the size of the microtext is different, researches also pay attention to this issue. A group of researchers (L.G. Friedman, etc.) consider the paragraph a large syntactic unit [Friedman, 1975, 217]. Others deny this idea. For example, according to L.M. Loseva, a paragraph cannot be a syntactic category. Because it is related to the composition of the written text [Loseva, 1969, 20]. The composition of the text consists of phrases and sentences. In addition, one paragraph can contain several microtexts or vice versa. Because the size of the paragraph

depends on the style of the author or the style of the text, it consists of one or two sentences or several pages.

The size and limit of the microtext is determined by some researchers (such as Heidolph K.E.) based on its communicative integrity [Heidolph, 1966]. Some scientists (Harweg R. and others) are based on the structural integrity of the text. In this case, in the first sentence of each microtext, the hero (person) of the work is usually expressed by a proper noun. In the following sentences, a pronoun is used [Harweg R., 1971].

From a brief review, it becomes clear that microtext integrity in foreign (German, Russian) languages has been sufficiently studied both theoretically and practically. In Uzbek linguistics, the structural integrity of the microtext has not been studied at all. Content and communicative integrity are partially researched. Now, on the basis of direct and indirect translation, we will proceed to the textual, syntactic and comparative-typological analysis of the second type of appropriation.

Let's start the analysis with microtexts containing two second type forms. First of all, we will try to define the limit of the microtext. For this purpose, we find sentences with opening words: In his eyes, the only task for now is to conduct the first meeting better, to prepare for it better (75). The key words in this sentence (meeting, readiness) are repeated in the sentence at the end of the first paragraph on page 81 (meeting, announcement): Saida calmed down and wrote an announcement about the meeting the next day.

Shularga tayanib mikromatnning mazmuniy asosini *Majlisga tayyorgarlik* deb nomlasa bo'ladi. Mazkur gaplardan mikromatnning hajmi ham aniq bo'ladi. U besh sahifadan ortiqroq, o'nlab abzatsdan tarkib topgan. Har bir abzats bittadan o'ntagacha va undan ortiq gapni o'z ichiga oladi. Mikromatnning mazmuniy yaxlitligini shakllantirishda takror bilan birga almashish, tejash (implikatsiya) vositalari ham ishtirok etadi. Kommunikativ maqsad kategoriyasining barcha ma'nosi (xabar, buyruq, so'roq) voqelangan. Gaplarni o'zaro mazmunan va shaklan birlashtirish uchun bog'lovchi va bog'lovchi vazifasidagi so'zlar qatnashgan.

Bularning barchasini izohlash bir necha sahifani band etadi. Shu sababli faqat o'zlashtirmalik va u bilan aloqador semalar namoyon bo'ladigan abzatsu gaplarni tahlil qilish bilan chegaralanamiz:

*Chunki bir vaqt Ismoiljon birmuncha masalalarda rais bilan kelisholmay uning nazaridan **qolgan**, yaxshi brigadir bo'lsa ham yelkasiga o'tob **tegmas ekan**.*
(80)

This example consists of one subordinate clause and one subordinate clause at the end of a ten-line paragraph. First of all, all the sentences in the paragraph express a message, that is, a sentence. However, in the first sentences, the direct message, i.e., the events that Saida, who came as a speaker, did or witnessed, is reported. Then two forms are used to convey the message.

One of the forms is *-gan*, and the other is *-(a)r*. *-mas* is the undivided form of the second participle. In the first form, the incomplete verb is saved. So there is an implication, which participates in forming the formal and substantive integrity of both sentences. In both forms, the themes of the past tense and assimilative message are manifested. The first theme is also expressed through a lexical tool (a time). It clarifies the tense understood from the morphological tool (*-gan*). At the same time, the second figure shows the extent of the continuity scheme. Since the form is in the second sentence, the lexical tool is part of the first sentence, the lexical tool participates in the formation of the temporal relationship between the two sentences.

In both sentences, it is clear that the speaker describes the action that happened in the past tense. But it is not clear whose opinion the speaker is expressing. A lexical device (*ba`zilar*) is used in the previous sentence to show the person whose opinion is appropriated. The speaker is represented by a proper noun (*Saida*) at the beginning of the paragraph. So, Saida is adopting the message he heard from others in another speech act and making it come true through two sentences. In other words, in the report of some people that *bir vaqt Ismoiljon birmuncha masalalarda rais bilan kelisholmay uning nazaridan qolgan **edi**, yaxshi brigadir bo'lsa ham yelkasiga o'tob tegmas **edi***, the speaker only changes the incomplete verb. As a result, the message

that some directly observed has partially changed and turned into a misappropriation message.

It should also be said that the connector (*chunki*) at the beginning of the example is performing the task of connecting the mastered message part of the microtext with the unmastered message part. In other words, it serves as a means of connecting the second part of the paragraph with the first part.

Now let's look at the direct translation of the example selected for analysis:

Дело в том, что когда-то, правда уже давно, Исмаилджан совершил довольно редкий в их колхозе проступок – покритиковал председателя – и с тех пор был у него в опале, хотя и продолжал оставаться одним из лучших бригадиров. (169)

The size of the paragraph included in the example corresponds to the original. The paragraph is ten lines long in both sources. But the example itself is three lines in the original and five lines in the translation. The reason is that the writer's use of every word was not taken into account. As a result, two or more words were used instead of one word in the original. For example *chunki – дело в том, что, bir vaqt – когда-то, правда уже давно* was translated. Added words missing from the original: *довольно редкий в колхозе*. The word (*rais*) denoting the social function of another person has been replaced by his last name. In addition, the nature of the translation language requires the expression of some additional meaning in words. The means of expression of the meaning of such continuity was *-(a)r (-mas)* in the original version, but it was translated into Russian by the word (*продолжал*). The source of the message is one word (*ba`zilar*) in the Uzbek text, and two words *двое или трое* in the translation. However, the intended concept could be expressed in Russian with one word, etc. The German translation corresponds exactly to the Russian one. It also contains all the vocabulary errors in the Russian translation. Including two words (*bir vaqt*) turned into four words (*freilich schon lange her*). Words not in the original have been added (*eine in der Kolchose ziemlich seltene Fehlleistung*), etc. The grammatical possibilities of the German language were not

used at all in the expression of the assimilated message, it was limited only to the lexical tool, as in the Russian language. The negative attitude of the senior leader (*rais*) to the junior leader (*brigadir*) is exaggerated. Russian translators used vocabulary and hyphens, while German translators added tone (*yozuvda undov belgisi*) and so on.

In der Tat, es war freilich schon lange her, hatte Ismaildshan eine in der Kolchose ziemlich seltene Fehlleistung begangen – er hatte den Vorsitzenden kritisiert! Seitdem lebte er in Ungnade, obwohl er weiterhin zu den besten Brigadieren gehörte. (66)

As a conclusion, it should be said that if the sentence and the context do not allow for a more precise analysis of the misappropriation, the microtext is referred to. Microtext represents a complete thought, unlike a sentence and context. Its communicative integrity is formed in two ways. First of all, the microtext consists of a chain connection of its components. Each subsequent sentence in the microtext communicatively continues the information based on the preceding sentence. As a result, a theme-rhematic chain is formed, the end of which marks the limit of the microtext.

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